

PROBING INTERFACE FAILURE MECHANISMS IN TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES USING SPATIALLY VARIED INTERFACES

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KEYWORDS: Metal Matrix Composites, Interface Engineering, Fatigue crack growth, transverse tensile strength, coatings, mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Spatially Varied Interfaces is a design concept for composite engineering whereby the interface mechanical response is tailored to the composite needs by varying the interface properties in patterns of weak and strong areas. In the SiC_f/Ti-alloy system, the longitudinal fatigue crack growth and transverse tensile behavior have been modified in a controlled manner using the SVI technique. The results of these experiments have enabled a better understanding of the stress states and interface failure mechanisms, and constitute a novel probe of interface failure mechanisms.

ABSTRACT

Titanium Matrix Composites (TMC's) are being developed for aircraft gas turbine engine compressor rotor rings, with up to 70% weight savings over conventional nickel-based superalloys. Two key mechanical properties for this component are the longitudinal fatigue life and the transverse tensile strength. The mechanical behavior of the interface between the fiber and matrix plays a large role in the failure process in each of these modes: In transverse tension, a strong interface enables the fiber to contribute to the composite strength to higher strength levels, and is therefore desirable from this standpoint. However, from a fatigue standpoint, a weaker interface is desired to promote easy debonding and crack bridging by the fiber. For both of these processes, the exact mechanism by which interface failure occurs is not well-understood. An experimental technique employing Spatially Varied Interfaces (SVI) has been developed that enables probing of these failure mechanisms by carefully positioning selectively weakened interface regions in single fiber-and single lamina composites. For this study, a striped SVI geometry was used, whereby a 70 μ m wide stripe of yttrium, which bonds weakly to Ti was coated onto a Textron ® SCS-0 fiber, which forms a strong bond with titanium.

In the case of transverse tension, the SVI experiments have demonstrated that interface shear failure precedes normal interface separation, contrary to conventional belief. In the case of fatigue crack growth, a comparison of striped-SVI samples with uncoated SCS-0 samples demonstrated that interface debonding ahead of the crack tip occurs, and that an interface that is only partially weak (that is, only part of the area), can still promote fiber crack bridging (see figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1 : da/dN vs. ΔK_a for the SVI coated SCS-0/Ti-6Al-4V composite compared to a sample comprised only of un-modified SCS-0 fibers. Fiber bridging of the crack is evident for the SVI composite, as the crack growth rate slows to 10^{-9} m/cycle. At the same load, the un-modified SCS-0 single lamina composite did not exhibit fiber bridging.

Fig. 2: Scanning electron microscope images of the fracture surface of SVI coated SCS-0/ Ti-6Al-4V showing striped SVI and un-modified SCS-0 fibers: a) Debonding and pull-out of the striped SVI fibers is greater than that of the un-modified SCS-0; b) Higher magnification of an SVI fiber reveals surface relief corresponding to the Y-stripe; and c) Higher magnification of the un-modified SCS-0 shows no relief and very little fiber pull out.